

YASHIL

**IQTISODIYOT
va
TARAQQIYOT**

*Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik,
ilmiy, ommabop jurnal*

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RIVOJLANTIRISHDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBI,
IQTISODIY TAHLIL VA AUDITNING ROLI HAMDA
ISTIQBOLDAGI VAZIFALAR" MAVZUSIDAGI
XALQARO ILMIY-AMALIY KONFERENSIYA**

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DIGITALIZATION IN AUDIT PROFESSION

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Abstract: This thesis explores the ways in which digitization affects the audit process, cybersecurity, AI (artificial intelligence), and data analytics. As a result, this thesis will analyze how digitization affects the various audit process components. Consequently, we also offer a study of the potential effects of this change on the assurance level, as reported by the auditor in the audit report. The thesis also analyzes the abilities that the future auditor in a digital environment will need to possess.

Key words: AI, data analytics, digitalization, big data, cybersecurity.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu dissertatsiya kiberxavsizlik, suniy intellekt va ma'lumotlar tahlilini qo'llashga urg'u berib, raqamlashtirishning audit jarayoniga ta'sir qilish usullarini o'rganadi. Natijada, ushbu tezis raqamlashtirish audit jarayonining turli qismlariga qanday ta'sir qilishini tahlil qiladi. Shunday qilib, biz auditorlik hisobotida auditor tomonidan bildirilgan ishonch darajasiga ushbu o'zgarishning mumkin bo'lgan ta'sirini o'rganishni ham taklif qilamiz. Dissertatsiya shuningdek, raqamli muhitda bo'lajak auditor ega bo'lishi kerak bo'lgan qobiliyatlarni tahlil qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: AI, ma'lumotlar tahlili, raqamlashtirish, katta ma'lumotlar, kiberxavsizlik.

Аннотация: В этой диссертации исследуется влияние цифровизации на процесс аудита, кибербезопасность, искусственного интеллекта и анализа данных. В результате в этой диссертации будет проанализировано, как цифровизация влияет на различные компоненты процесса аудита. Следовательно, мы также предлагаем исследование потенциального воздействия этого изменения на уровень уверенности, о чем сообщает аудитор в аудиторском отчете. В диссертации также анализируются способности, которыми необходимо будет обладать будущему аудитору в цифровой среде.

Ключевые слова: ИИ, аналитика данных, цифровизация, большие данные, кибербезопасность.

As technology advances and blurs the boundaries between the conceivable and the imagined, digitalization has become more significant in our ever-changing world. Technical advancements open up new options, which transform the world. Today, the most powerful force driving social transformation may be the globalization of society. Organizations that will function in the future will be formed by this shift, where practitioners will need to rely increasingly more on information and communication (Luliana & Tugui, 2005)). As well as, businesses compile their financial statements using a framework of nationally applicable generally accepted accounting principles (GAAP), often known as accounting standards or financial reporting standards. An audit is a particular type of examination that is carried out by an individual other than the parties concerned as part of establishing accountability.

AI: The definition of artificial intelligence (AI) is machine intelligence. According to computer science, the perfect "intelligent" machine is a flexible, rational agent that observes its surroundings and makes decisions that will increase its chances of achieving a certain objective. The phrase "artificial intelligence" is typically used to describe situations in which a machine simulates "cognitive" tasks, such as "learning" and "problem solving," that people identify with the brains of other humans. (H. Issa and others, 2016).

AI is presently being used in many different fields, such as investment portfolio management, home energy systems, and vehicle-free zones. In addition, accounting and auditing will be impacted. The following succinctly describes how artificial intelligence has affected the audit profession: (E&Y, 2018)

- Developing models based on sophisticated machine learning auditors can enhance fraud detection; • Accounting transactions can be automatically recorded by machine learning.
- AI is capable of analyzing unstructured data, like audio files from conference calls, social media posts, and emails.
- AI will help auditors make the most of their time so they can apply human judgment to examine a larger and more in-depth range of information and documents.

Data analytics: Big data are datasets that are too large for standard database software tools to handle, store, collect, and analyze, McKinsey (2011). More significantly, big data for auditors refers to the gathering of various forms of data, which could include a combination of conventionally organized financial and non-financial data, logistics data, sensor data, emails, phone conversations, social media data, blogs, and other internal and external data. Connolly (2012) takes the beginning point for transactions to be the typical focus of auditors on transactional data, and hence a particularly applicable content definition of big data in the audit context: (Alles and others, 2015),

Big Data consists of interactions, transactions, and observations. Big data offers more pertinent company insights and audit proof of a better caliber. With the use of big data and analytics, auditors may more effectively detect fraud, operational business hazards, and financial reporting, and they can modify their methodology to provide a more pertinent audit. Numerous forms of audit evidence can be added thanks to the automatic data collection processes provided by sensors, RFID (Radio Frequency Recognition), and GPS data streams. For instance, using data from RFID or barcode systems, one of the big data sources, makes it possible to monitor inventory costs in real-time rather than utilizing techniques like LIFO and FIFO to calculate inventory prices. The financial markets files, emails, websites, social media, and media news are some of the big data components. These data are instruments that aid in assessing and enhancing processing performance. (Özerhan and Aslan, 2017).

The term cybersecurity describes the precautions taken to guard against loss, damage, illegal access, and abuse by unauthorized individuals of firm data stored on computer-based systems. “Cybersecurity should be addressed in a holistic manner and systematically in all institutions,” according to the IIA handbook “2016 Global Perspectives and Understanding: Internal Audit as a Trusted Cyber Advisor.” This is because an institution’s inability to provide cybersecurity can result in inadequacy to carry out its most basic activities, loss of intellectual property rights, and even great damage to its reputation (IIA, 2016). Governments everywhere have realized that cybersecurity is becoming more and more crucial for private sector businesses as well as public sector, military, and vital national substructure organizations. In addition, cybersecurity poses a risk to businesses and technology. The biggest and most frequent danger that both public and private businesses in a variety of industries face nowadays is cyberattacks. Cybersecurity breaches can have an impact on the following:

- the brand and online assets via defamation, accusations, and secret revelation;
 - financial systems and assets through abuse, theft, and extortion;
 - intellectual property rights and company secrets through espionage;
- maintaining business continuity via operations disruption and sabotage

All of the individuals who were questioned are public accountants with state authorization; a few of them are even in charge of the audit innovation department inside their respective firms. It has been feasible to determine, based on the data acquired, that the areas where there is a possibility for disruption are specifically the audit’s execution and reporting of its results. Because professional skepticism is required, only a portion of the audit process may be automated, including the planning, final phase, and customer accept. The ability to verify every transaction, higher audit quality, fraud detection potential, and enhanced audit planning are the main advantages of employing digital technologies. The requirements for data availability, data security, and the necessary abilities for using digital technologies provide obstacles to these advantages. Furthermore, the thesis emphasizes how new digital tool utilization is right now. We conclude that the assurance in the audit report should not even be raised or lowered, but rather should be maintained in light of this, the accounting assumptions, and the risk of fraud. We determine that the assurance in the audit report should be maintained despite the fact that digital tools enable testing of all transactions, which may present a chance to increase the assurance in the report. These reasons include the risk of defective material, disciplinary responsibility, and auditor liability. The audit process is moving more and more toward the use of digital tools, so prospective auditors must also acquire the skills required. These skills include knowing how the tools operate and how to incorporate them into the various stages of the audit process. The auditor can acquire these skills through study and by collaborating with experts.

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